

MUSIC SCIENCE IN THE LITERARY ENVIRONMENT OF BUKHARA (XIX-XX CENTURIES)

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Annotation: This article shows that Bukhara is a blessed place that has been able to deliver a number of high-ranking hafiz and artistic musicians to the world singing. It was stated that Shashmaqom and folklore songs created on this land have a special place in introducing the name of Bukhara to the world.

Key words: music, arithmetic, handasa, nagma, mutaarif, singing, art, tarona, tabiyat, poetry, muhammaskhan, zaki, alloma, sozanda, Bukhara, dubayti, rubai

Аннотация: В данной статье показано, что Бухара – благословенное место, способное дать мировому пению ряд высокопоставленных хафизов и артистических музыкантов. Было отмечено, что Шашмаком и фольклорные песни, созданные на этой земле, занимают особое место в ознакомлении мира с названием Бухары.

Ключевые слова: музыка, арифметика, хандаса, нагма, мутаариф, пение, искусство, тарона, табият, поэзия, мухаммасхан, заки, аллома, созанда, Бухара, дубайти, рубаи.

The basics of music sometimes come from arithmetic. However, the edges of zum arba, zul khams and other bods are proportional to each other. Some of them are from geometry. For example, we say that the pitch and height of the strings are calculated depending on the length and length of the string. And sometimes from the science of nature (psychology). Because the power of a person's will comes from his feelings and actions. And some of them are from the knowledge of mutaarif (tradition).

Abduqadir Maroghi, "Maqasid ul-alhan"

From time immemorial, our people have expressed their hatred for evil by singing all the processes of their life. He even greeted the change of seasons with songs and brought up the new born baby with the help of songs. Every change in a child's life is recorded through songs. In particular, the songs dedicated to the young generation, who have reached the level of family building and found their own happiness, attract everyone's attention with their impressiveness. Even when a person is separated from his closest person, he follows him to his final destination, crying and singing about his loss. So, singing is closely connected

with people's life in this way and covers all spheres of social life. They are responsible for every social event that happens in the marriage.

Singing, which has been forming in Bukhara for a long time, has risen to the level of art in the region. A number of mature manifestations of it have matured and established their own traditions. Under these traditions, the ability to sing has been deeply ingrained in the blood and consciousness of the youth of this time and has been passed down from generation to generation.

Another aspect is that "taronas" is an ancient symbol of Eastern classical music, besides, it is one of the veins of the huge musical system called "Shashmaqom". Taronas - tarannums (both come from the same root) actually means "life song", in today's parlance, "worldly song". According to Hazrat Nawai, taronas are also called "Dubayti" or "Rubai". So, Shashmaqom is one of the rivers that give life to the sea. So, this is the demand of the time, the requirement of the era.

Many scholars have written about the science of shashmaqom. In the turbulent times of the 20th century, a famous scholar like Abdurauf Fitrat tried to create a scientific work on the topic of "Uzbek classical music and its history". He was able to achieve much success. However, the people of the time did not allow these actions to be realized, and they were violated. As a result, the science of music was temporarily forced to retreat.

Sharifjon Makhdom (Sadr Zia), Sadridin Ainiy, and Abdurauf Fitrat led the literary environment of Bukhara in the 20th century.

One of the musical genres of Bukhara, which is part of the musical folklore of Bukhara and is being improved, which belongs only to Bukhara - the art of "Bukhara" and "Mavrigi" is also a literary-musical source worthy of scientific and practical research. Under the influence of Shashmaqom, the most advanced example of classical music, a number of classical music groups have appeared in the land of ancient and modern Bukhara. In particular, it can be seen that at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, in the palace of the emir of Bukhara, a high example of women's art, the art of "sozanda", that is, the "Bukhara" series, appeared. In the cultural environment of the Bukhara palace, women were famous for their poetry, muhammaskhan (recitation of poetry) and the performance of the series "Bukhorcha" at their special parties. The art of music, which is directly related to women's creative and performing activities, was also established.

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in the circle, and a new - the second mukhammashon took his turn. Fours have the essence of love and loyalty, the generosity of wedding guests, and the essence of gossip. Usually, the limit of this type of muhammaskhana depended on the number of people who agreed to say muhammas to a solo dancer: the more people said muhammas, the greater the response.

Today, our primary task is to study the blessed steps of this sacred musical heritage, its true and life-giving roots, scientific-theoretical, practical and creative foundations. At the same time, it is necessary to restore the unjustified and forgotten true scientific views and bring them to the attention of young musicians and artists.

Shashmaqom is a huge complex based on real scientific foundations - a capital of musical art. Two types of its meaning and content as a musical genre are mentioned in the book "Maqasidu-l-alhan" by Abdul Qadir Maroghi. However, Kulliyat, a category of multi-part works described in Kavkabi's treatise, is similar in content to Musical Shashmaqom, that is, it is recorded as a generalized set of actual parts (status, voice, branch) and method structures. Later, in Darvesh Ali's treatise, it is noted that Kavkabi is the creator of the unique complex "Kulliyot", which surprised his contemporaries, and mentions the names of teachers who followed in his footsteps and created magnificent works in this field.

And finally, the 19th century Bukhara musical treatise - bayozy (hereafter referred to as concise treatise-bayoz or musical bayoz) due to time constraints, as far as we know, the first copy was created in 1847. It is a two-part manuscript whose author is unknown. In the small prose piece, the role of Maulana Kavkabi Bukhari in the field of music is emphasized, and Kulliyot is recognized as one of the royal works of his artistic creation. The poetic text of this work, written by Kavkabi, is also presented. Here, the scientific part of the treatise comes to an end, and it goes to its poetic section, saying "endi shashmaqom" ("aknun shashmaqom").

In the 40s of the 19th century, the famous orientalist A.A. Semyonov tried to restore the idea of the existence of an integral connection between "Musiqi shashmakom" and "Kulliyoti" of Kavkabi, described in Bukhara treatises. But the politicians, who are far from the science of music, destroyed the effective ideas by accusing the selfless scientist's efforts of "caving". It is forbidden to attach to his thoughts and ideas, even to mention his name. For this reason, the issue of relations between Kulliyot and Shashmaqom was forced out of the scientific field.

Now is the time to openly discuss the issues related to the roots of our national musical heritage, to restore closed opinions and opinions. For this reason, the time has come to restore the real source and name badges of "Musical Shashmaqom", which is the foundation of the authority's property.

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